

Call 1 link to the Euraxess website

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D3.1 CALL 1 LINK TO THE EURAXESS WEBSITE

Grant Agreement n°:	101126533
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Project acronym:	TOUCH
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Project title:	Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH
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Funding Scheme:	MSCA-COFUND-2022 (DOCTORAL PROGRAMME)
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Project Duration:	2024/02/01 – 2029/01/31 (60 months)
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Beneficiary:	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
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Implementing partners:	Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CED) Centre de Recerca Matemàtica (CRM) Centre de Visió per Computador (CVC) Fundació Salut i Envel·liment (FSIE) Institut d'Investigació i Innovació Parc Taulí (I3PT) Institut de Recerca Sant Pau (IR Sant Pau) Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca (VHIR)
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Project no. 101126533

TOUCH

Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH

MSCA-COFUND-2022 (DOCTORAL PROGRAMME)

Start date of project: 01/02/2024 Duration: 60 months

History Chart				
Issue	Date	Changed page(s)	Cause of change	Implemented by
1.0	15/3/2024	-	Draft	UAB
2.0	20/3/2024	-	Version 2.0	UAB

Validation			
No.	Action	Beneficiary	Date
1	Prepared	UAB	15 March 2024
2	Approved	UAB	20 March 2024
3	Released	UAB	21 March 2024

Disclaimer

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Call 1 link to the EURAXESS website

The TOUCH programme job offers were published on the EURAXESS website on 15 March 2024. The announcement showed all the information required by the candidates to apply for the positions offered. It described in detail the predoctoral programme, research and training activities, partner institutions, eligibility criteria, employment conditions, selection process, and provided detailed instructions on how to apply through the [TOUCH website](#). The job advertisement can be consulted in the following link to the EURAXESS platform post: <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/205238>, and it is also shown in Annex 1: TOUCH EURAXESS announcement.

In addition to the TOUCH announcement, each of the 34 positions offered by the programme in the first call was published individually on the EURAXESS portal. Besides the aforementioned general information, the individual posts included a comprehensive explanation of the research project, supervisors, research group and the skills and certification needed for a competitive application. See below for the links and publication date of each job advertisement (Table 1). A screenshot of the TOUCH EURAXESS account showing the publication information of the posted job offers is given in Annex 2: job offers published on the TOUCH EURAXESS account.

TOPIC (INSTITUTION)	LINK	PUBLICATION DATE
Improving psychosis risk detection through artificial intelligence (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204817	14 March 2024
Molecular determinants of sex- and neuropsychiatric-specific vulnerability to cognitive disability during aging (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204821	14 March 2024
Neuroimaging and personality in Clinical and Health Psychology (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204857	14 March 2024
Migrant's mental healthcare and multilevel personal networks (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204860	14 March 2024
A transdisciplinary multi-scalar approach to foster mental in Europe by means of nature-based therapies (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204863	14 March 2024
Predictive processing, creativity and mental health (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204870	14 March 2024
Critical intersections of health, vulnerability, and discomfort in education: touching the students' lives with arts-based autobiography to build a caring university community (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/206146	19 March 2024
Nourishing Cognitive Resilience: Investigating Diet and Biomarkers in Midlife Aging (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204878	14 March 2024
The mind-body connection: Bridging the gap between lifestyle factors and cognitive wellbeing from clinical to demographic analysis (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204879	15 March 2024
Inflammageing, Cognitive Function, and Brain Health: Assessing the Effects of a Dietary Intervention (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204881	14 March 2024
Healthy Entourages throughout Athletic Careers (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204882	14 March 2024

Precarious employment trajectories, psychosocial risks, and mental wellbeing (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204885	14 March 2024
Mindful Collaboration: Shaping Care Strategies through Mental Health User Involvement (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204888	14 March 2024
Consumption of ultra-processed foods and drinks and major depressive disorder through gut microbiota-brain axis (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204891	14 March 2024
Single-cell calcium imaging and machine learning in fear memory models (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/205164	15 March 2024
Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder and borderline intellectual disability children: cognitive, biological, and emotional correlates (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/205169	15 March 2024
Psychopathic-traits and prosociality in a community sample of children: biological and emotional correlates (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/205176	15 March 2024
Developing New Models and Measures of Genetic and Psychological Sensitivity to the Psychosocial Environment to Understand both Risk and Resilience in Mental Health (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/205185	15 March 2024
Dissecting the contribution of dysregulated sense of agency to psychotic disorders (UAB)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/205187	15 March 2024
Mental health of dependent people with chronic diseases (CED)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204720	14 March 2024
Mental health and multimorbidity in Catalonia (CED)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204727	14 March 2024
Computational modeling of working memory decline in normal aging (CRM)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204734	14 March 2024
Mathematical modelling of disease trajectories across modalities (CRM)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204758	14 March 2024
Modelling circular inference, from the general population to psychotic experience (CRM)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204766	14 March 2024
Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for Mental Health Support (CVC)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204768	14 March 2024
A deeper understanding of human cognition and mental health through AI and Data Science (CVC)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204770	14 March 2024
Enhancing Elderly Mental Health through Reminiscence Therapy and Robotic Companionship (FSIE)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204777	14 March 2024
Assessing the Impact and Effectiveness of the AMICOPE Multicomponent Community Intervention on Mood in Older Adults: A Mixed Methods Approach (FSIE)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204785	14 March 2024
Prevention, follow-up and management of post-ICU sequelae based on digital health tools (I3PT)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204793	14 March 2024
The digital transformation in primary care and specialized mental health centers through artificial intelligent/machine learning tools for the prevention and monitoring of patients at risk of suicide in Catalonia (I3PT)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204801	14 March 2024
Integrative Omics and Neuroimaging of Treatment Resistance in Psychiatric Disorders: An AI Approach (IR Sant Pau)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204807	14 March 2024

Caregiver-Centric Innovations in Intensive Home-Treatment for Acute Mental Illness: A Comprehensive Approach (IR Sant Pau)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/204812	14 March 2024
Intergenerational transmission of psychopathology: Effects of parental genotypes (VHIR)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/205201	15 March 2024
Usefulness of multidomain markers in the course of post stroke and neurodegenerative dementias (VHIR)	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/205206	15 March 2024

Table 1: list of TOUCH job offers for the first call showing the links to their EURAXESS publications and the dates of publication.

EURAXESS

- [Home](#) | [Jobs and Funding](#) ▾ | [Career Development](#) | [Partnering](#) ▾ | [Information and Assistance](#) ▾ | [National Portals](#) | [Worldwide](#) ▾

[Home](#) > [Jobs & Funding](#) >

13 PhD positions on mental health and wellbeing in the framework of the TOUCH COFUND project led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

13 PhD positions on mental health and wellbeing in the framework of the TOUCH COFUND project led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

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[Where to apply](#)

[Contact](#)

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

15 MAR 2024

Job Information

Organisation/Company	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
Research Field	Psychological sciences Biological sciences Neurosciences Demography Sociology Medical sciences Computer science
Researcher Profile	First Stage Researcher (R1)
Country	Spain
Application Deadline	30 Jun 2024 - 23:59 (Europe/Madrid)
Type of Contract	Temporary
Job Status	Full-time
Is the job funded through the EU Research Framework Programme?	H2020 / Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions COFUND
Marie Curie Grant Agreement Number	101126530
Is the Job related to staff position within a Research Infrastructure?	No

Offer Description

The [TOUCH](#) doctoral programme is offering 13 three-year pre-doctoral fellowships. TOUCH ("Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH") is a new excellent doctoral programme coordinated by the [Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona](#) (UAB) and co-funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie (MSCA) Actions of the European Commission (EC). Its main goal is the recruitment and training of doctoral candidates in the field of **mental health and wellbeing** providing a new dimension through highly interdisciplinary and intersectoral research while fulfilling all the principles of Open Science and maintaining the highest research quality standards. TOUCH involves the UAB and 7 reference organisations as implementing partners hosting doctoral students (research centres, research foundations and research organisations linked to prestigious hospitals in the region): [Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics](#), [Centre de Recerca Matemàtica](#), [Centre de Visió per Computador](#), [Fundació Salut i Entorn UAB](#), [Institut d'Investigació i Innovació Parc Taulí](#), [Institut de Recerca Sant Pau](#), and [Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca](#).

We are looking for candidates with an **excellent CV**, a high degree of **ambition and motivation**, and with **good personal qualities** to join the TOUCH doctoral programme. We offer a three-year full-time contract (37,5 hours / week) and a gross salary of 2.375 €/month (the salary will be the same for the 3 years). The successful candidates will be enrolled in a doctoral program at the UAB and will be involved in the TOUCH training activities, including: (i) workshops and practical hands-on schools, (ii) training in scientific and communication skills, research diversity and a personal development retreat, among other activities to bring a holistic approach to the training through a combination of research-oriented and challenging soft skills, and (iii) international and/or intersectoral secondments at partner laboratories and premises.

The candidates must fulfil the following eligibility criteria from the EC: **Mobility rule:** candidates must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in Spain for more than 12 months in the 36 months immediately preceding the deadline for the programme call. **Experience rule:** researchers must be doctoral candidates at the date of recruitment, i.e. not already in possession of a doctoral degree at the deadline of the open calls. Researchers who have successfully defended their doctoral thesis but have not yet formally awarded the doctoral degree will not be considered eligible. **The candidates must hold a degree that allows admission to the official doctoral programme at UAB.** Additional academic and skills requirements for each position can be found in the "[offered PhD positions](#)" section on the TOUCH website.

Interested applicants should apply through the TOUCH online platform by submitting a full CV, a motivation letter, two letters of recommendation and academic and English level certificates. The call will be open from the 1st of April to the 30th of June 2024. More information about the TOUCH project, the recruitment process, and the application platform are available on the [TOUCH website](#).

Requirements

Research Field	Psychological sciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Neurosciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Biological sciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Medical sciences
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Demography
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Sociology
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Research Field	Computer science
Education Level	Master Degree or equivalent
Languages	ENGLISH
Level	Excellent

Additional Information

Work Location(s)

Number of offers available	1
Company/Institute	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
Country	Spain
City	Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona)
Geofield	

Webtools | © EC-GISCO | Leaflet | © OpenStreetMap contributors | Disclaimer

Where to apply

Website	https://webs.uab.cat/touch/
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Contact

State/Province	Barcelona
City	Cerdanyola del Vallès
Website	http://www.uab.cat
Street	Campus UAB
Postal Code	08193
E-Mail	pr.cofund.touch@uab.cat

ANNEX 2: job offers published on the TOUCH EURAXESS account

Title	Content type	Status	Moderation state	Updated ▼	Operations
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	18/03/2024 - 15:33	Edit node
13 PhD positions on mental health and wellbeing in the framework of the TOUCH COFUND project led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	Job Offer	Published	Published	18/03/2024 - 09:13	Edit node
PhD position at Vall d'Hebron Research Institute funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 14:37	Edit node
PhD position at Vall d'Hebron Research Institute funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 14:22	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 13:58	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 13:58	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 13:07	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 13:07	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 13:07	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 08:27	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 08:27	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 08:26	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 08:26	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 08:26	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	15/03/2024 - 08:26	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 16:20	Edit node

Title	Content type	Status	Moderation state	Updated ▾	Operations
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 16:20	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 15:53	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 15:53	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 15:52	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 13:38	Edit node
PhD position at Institut de Recerca Sant Pau funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 13:25	Edit node
PhD position at Institut de Recerca Sant Pau funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 13:25	Edit node
PhD position at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 13:24	Edit node
PhD position at Institute for Research and Innovation Parc Taulí I3PT funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 12:48	Edit node
PhD position at Institute for Research and Innovation Parc Taulí I3PT funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 12:42	Edit node
PhD position at Computer Vision Center funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 12:31	Edit node
PhD position at Centre Recerca Matemàtica funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 12:31	Edit node
PhD position at Centre Recerca Matemàtica funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 12:31	Edit node
PhD position at Computer Vision Center funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 12:31	Edit node
PhD position at Health and Ageing Foundation UAB funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 12:30	Edit node
PhD position at Health and Ageing Foundation UAB funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 12:30	Edit node
PhD position at Centre Recerca Matemàtica funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 11:32	Edit node
PhD position at Centre for Demographic Studies funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 10:52	Edit node
PhD position at Centre for Demographic Studies funded by the TOUCH COFUND project	Job Offer	Published	Published	14/03/2024 - 10:52	Edit node